

ESTIMATION OF ACETALDEHYDE BY HYPOIODITE OXIDATION

BY SAMEER BOSE

A procedure is described for estimating acetaldehyde by oxidising it to acetic acid with a solution of sodium hypoiodite containing a good deal of free iodine. The analytical precision is 0.8% or better. The method is also applicable in presence of acetone or ethyl alcohol. It can be used with a slight modification for micro-estimation, suitable for evaluating quantities as low as 0.13 mg. of the aldehyde.

Romijn (*Z. anal. Chem.*, 1897, 36, 18) described a method of estimating formaldehyde by oxidation with sodium hypoiodite. The method when applied to acetaldehyde failed, although several attempts were made by various workers. Hatcher and Mueller (*Trans. Roy. Soc. Canada*, 1929, 3-23, 35-44) reported that under most favourable conditions only 60% results were obtained. Mitchell *et. al.* ("Organic Analysis," 1953, Vol. 1, p. 267) summarised the efforts in this direction and concluded that the reaction between acetaldehyde and alkaline iodine solution was not stoichiometric, although it was reproducible. The present work was undertaken to investigate the factors affecting the reaction and to determine its applicability in the quantitative estimation of acetaldehyde. On investigation it was found that when solutions of acetaldehyde and sodium hypoiodite containing excess of alkali were mixed, two simultaneous reactions occurred. One is the oxidation of the aldehyde molecule to acetic acid, and another is the substitution of iodine in the molecule leading to the formation of iodoform. The 60% results, reported previously, were based on the assumption that only the latter reaction had occurred.

In the present investigation, an attempt has been made to suppress the iodoform reaction and to oxidise the aldehyde quantitatively to acetic acid. This has been achieved by using insufficient quantity of alkali. Although it was not possible to completely stop the iodine substitution, but it was limited to 0.2-0.3% of the aldehyde, as found from the actual estimation of the iodoform produced; 99.7-99.8% of the aldehyde was oxidised quantitatively.

EXPERIMENTAL

An iodine solution of 0.1 N was prepared by dissolving 12.7 g. of iodine in 40 c.c of water containing 16 g. of KI and making up the volume to 1 litre. For micro-estimation, a 0.01N solution was prepared by diluting the 0.1 N solution.

Hypo solutions of 0.1 N and 0.01 N were prepared and standardised against dichromate. Six solutions of acetaldehyde were prepared by diluting a pure sample of the aldehyde with conductivity water. The solutions were standardised by Schultes' method (*Z. angew. Chem.*, 1934, 47, 258) using hydroxylamine sulphate and bromophenol blue as indicator.

Sodium hydroxide and sulphuric acid taken were of A. R. quality. Two solutions were prepared from each, one of 1.0 N and another of 0.10 N, exactly.

Procedure.—The solution (10 c.c.) containing not more than 17 mg. of acetaldehyde was pipetted into a 150 c.c. conical flask and treated with 20-50 c.c. of 0.1*N* iodine solution. The amount of iodine added was about 8 times the quantity theoretically required (2.2 mg. requires 1 c.c. I₂). The mixture was made alkaline by adding dropwise 1 to 2.8 c.c. of 1.0*N*-NaOH from a burette at the rate of 1 drop per second. During the addition of the alkali drops the contents of the flask were vigorously shaken by giving it a circular motion. Insufficient quantity of alkali was used so as to react with only about half of the iodine, the other half remaining free. Later the flask was well corked and kept standing for 10-15 minutes at about 25° and then its contents were acidified with 1.0*N*-H₂SO₄ using only 0.2 c.c. of the acid in excess. The iodine liberated was titrated with 0.1*N* hypo solution using starch as indicator. At the end, the solution became clear and no precipitate of iodoform was visible, only a very faint smell of it existed. A blank was run similar in all respects except for the addition of the aldehyde solution and, thus, the amount of iodine consumed by the acetaldehyde solution was found out. Each molecule of the aldehyde consumes 2 atoms of iodine as it oxidises to acetic acid.

$\text{CH}_3\text{CHO} + \text{I}_2 + 3 \text{NaOH} \rightarrow \text{CH}_3\text{COONa} + 2\text{NaI} + 2 \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (1 c.c. of 0.1 *N*-I₂ = 2.2 mg. of CH₃CHO).

The results obtained by the present method and those by Schultes' are compared in Table I. For the latter procedure the amount of aldehyde solution taken for estimation varied from 25 c.c. to 50 c.c.

TABLE I

Soln. No.	0.1 <i>N</i> -I ₂ added.	1 <i>N</i> -NaOH added.	0.1 <i>N</i> I ₂ consumed.	CH ₃ CHO found by		% Diff.
				Present method.	Schultes' method.	
1	50 c.c.	2.8 c.c.	7.50 c.c.	16.50 mg.	16.39 mg.	+0.67
2	50	2.6	6.20	13.64	13.53	+0.81
3	40	2.4	5.10	11.22	11.17	+0.45
4	40	2.2	4.95	8.91	8.86	+0.56
5	30	1.7	3.50	7.70	7.64	+0.78
6	25	1.4	3.05	6.71	6.66	+0.74

Estimation in presence of Acetone or Ethyl Alcohol.—The method is applicable in presence of acetone or ethyl alcohol provided that the hypoiodite solution is not allowed to react with these substances for a long time. The oxidation of acetaldehyde takes only about one minute at 25° when 0.1*N*-I₂ solution is used and the hypoiodite formed is about four times the amount theoretically required. Therefore in presence of acetone or ethyl alcohol the same procedure, as already described, was followed, the only difference being that after adding alkali the reaction mixture was kept standing at 25-27° for 2 minutes only and then acidified with 1*N*-H₂SO₄. If longer time was allowed, slightly higher results were obtained as the hypoiodite solution slowly attacked acetone or ethyl alcohol. Good results were obtained when the concentration of acetone on molality basis did not exceed that of the aldehyde. In case of ethyl alcohol the same was true when the concentration of the alcohol was not more than three times that of the aldehyde.

The results of estimation of mixtures of acetaldehyde and acetone (Expts. 1-4) as well as those of acetyldehyde and ethyl alcohol (Expts. 5-10) are recorded in Table II.

TABLE II

Temp. = 25-27°

(10 c.c. CH_3CHO mixture + 40 c.c. of 0.1N- I_2 + 2.4 c.c. of 1N-NaOH, kept 2 minutes and then acidified).

Expt. No.	Mol. proportion of CH_3CHO : acetone.	0.1N- I_2 consumed.	Acetaldehyde Found.	Present.	% Error.
1	4 : 1	6.00 c.c.	13.20 mg.	13.15 mg.	0.4
2	2 : 1	6.05	13.31	13.15	1.2
3	1 : 1	6.1	13.42	13.15	2.6
4	2 : 3	6.3	13.86	13.15	5.4
CH_3CHO : EtOH.					
5	1 : 1	6.00	13.20	13.15	0.4
6	2 : 3	6.05	13.31	13.15	1.2
7	1 : 2	6.05	13.31	13.15	1.2
8	2 : 5	6.10	13.42	13.15	2.0
9	1 : 3	6.15	13.53	13.15	2.9
10	2 : 7	6.20	13.64	13.15	3.8

Micro-estimation.—In a small conical flask 0.01N- I_2 solution (5-40 c.c.) was taken by a pipette and treated with 1-10 c.c. of the acetaldehyde solution containing not more than 1.4 mg. of the aldehyde. The amount of iodine used was about 6 times the quantity actually required (0.22 mg. requires 1 c.c. of I_2). The mixture was made alkaline by adding 0.1N-NaOH solution dropwise from a burette with vigorous swirling. The amount of alkali used was enough to react with about 80-90% of the iodine taken. A small portion of the iodine was invariably left unchanged. The flask was well corked and allowed to stand for 20 to 30 minutes at about 25° and then acidified with 0.1N- H_2SO_4 , using 0.5 c.c. in excess. The iodine liberated was titrated with 0.01 N hypo after adding through a pipette 2 c.c. of starch solution. In very dilute solutions the appearance as well as the disappearance of the blue colour caused by starch and iodine took a little time and therefore towards the end-point hypo solution was added slowly and after every drop the flask was shaken for about half a minute. In order to ensure the correct end-point, the solution was back-titrated by adding from a fast burette one drop (0.05 c.c.) of 0.01N iodine and the faint blue colour obtained on keeping for 5 minutes was compared with the one obtained under similar conditions in the blank, which was preserved. The blank was carried out in a very similar manner except for the addition of acetaldehyde. Thus, the amount of iodine consumed by a definite volume of the aldehyde solution was found. (1 c.c. of 0.01N- I_2 = 0.22 mg. of CH_3CHO).

The results of estimation of a 0.003M solution of acetaldehyde are recorded in Table III. For Expts. 1 and 2 a 10 c.c. micro-burette was used.

TABLE III

Expt. No.	CH ₃ CHO soln. taken (0.003 M)	0.01N-I ₂ added.	0.1N-NaOH added.	0.01N-I ₂ consumed.	CH ₃ CHO		% Error.
					Found.	Present.	
1	1 c.c.	5 c.c.	0.4 c.c.	0.6 c.c.	0.132 mg.	0.131 mg.	0.8
2	2	10	0.8	1.2	0.264	0.262	0.8
3	4	20	1.6	2.4	0.528	0.524	0.8
4	5	20	1.8	2.95	0.649	0.655	0.9
5	10	40	3.6	6.0	1.32	1.310	0.8

In conclusion it may be stated that the method described furnishes good and consistent results, if the alkali concentration is suitably adjusted. The titrations have the advantage of possessing a sharp end-point. The percentage of error is small, if a blank is carried out under identical conditions.

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CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
MAHAKOSHAL MAHABIDYALAYA,
JABALPUR., M.P.

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